

DEVELOPMENT OF LOW-COST PROTECTED STRUCTURE TO ENHANCE FARMERS INCOME

Dongardive S. N.^{1*}, Mohod A. G.², Khandetod Y. P.³, Dhande K. G.⁴, Thokal R. T.⁵

1*Ph.D. (REE) Scholar, CAET, DBSKKV, Dapoli, Maharashtra, India.

2 Department of Renewable Energy Engineering, CAET, DBSKKV, Dapoli, India.

3 Department of Renewable Energy Engineering, CAET, DBSKKV, Dapoli, Maharashtra, India.

4 Department of Farm Power and Machinery, CAET, DBSKKV, Dapoli, Maharashtra, India.

5 Department of Irrigation and drainage Engineering, AICRP, CES, Wakavali, Maharashtra, India.

snehaldongardive28@gmail.com

(MS Received: 28.01.2024; MS Revised: 03.03.2024; MS Accepted: 04.03.2024)

MS 3182

(RESEARCH PAPER IN RENEWABLE ENERGY ENGINEERING,)

Abstract

The use of low-cost protected structure for cultivating various cultivar varieties could play a significant role in the future of Indian agriculture. These greenhouses enable year-round cultivation, ensuring timely availability of cultivars with robust growth. A low-cost protected structure of 12.5 square meters was constructed (5m x 2.5m) using locally available materials. GI Square pipes was used as the structural material and UV stabilized polythene film replaced traditional glass sheets as the outer cover. The maximum inside and outside temperature and solar intensity of crop protective structure was found to be 35.98 °C and 33.34°C, respectively and 196.66 W/m² and 518.2 W/m² respectively during 20th MW. The maximum inside and outside relative humidity of crop protective structure was found to be 28.74% and 32.78 %, respectively during 14th MW.

Keywords: Protected structure, Controlled environment, Cladding Material, Temperature, Solar Intensity

Introduction

Growing plants is both an art and a science. About 95% of plants, either food crops or cash crops are grown in open field. Since time immemorial, man has learnt how to grow plants under natural environmental conditions. In some of the temperate regions where the climatic conditions are extremely adverse and no crops can be grown, man has developed methods of growing some high value crop continuously by providing protection from the excessive cold, which is called as Greenhouse Technology. So, Greenhouse Technology is the technique of providing favourable environment condition to the plants. It is rather used to protect the plants from the adverse climatic conditions such as wind, cold, precipitation, excessive radiation, extreme temperature, insects and diseases. It is also of vital importance to create an ideal micro climate around the plants. This is possible by erecting a greenhouse / glass house, where the environmental conditions are so modified that one can grow any plant in any place at any time by providing suitable environmental conditions with minimum labour. Greenhouses are framed or inflated structures covered with transparent or translucent material large enough to grow crops under partial or fully controlled environmental conditions to get optimum growth and productivity.

Materials and Methods**Criteria for selecting protective structure**

The galvanize iron (GI) pipe-based protective structure conform to ISI trade mark with minimum size 2 mm wall thickness was used with following features: (Greenhouse reference manual, 2011)

Stub type anchoring foundation, Galvanize and nut bolted structure having option for future expansion.

Strong enough to with stand various types of loads such as wind load, live load, crop load, dead load and snow load.

Aerodynamic shape along all peripheries to resist high wind speed.

The structure is design to resist wind velocity up to 150 km/hr.

Provision of fixing UV stabilized plastic film with aluminum and GI profile and zigzag spring lock.

Use 200 micron UV stabilized plastic film conforming to Indian standard IS 15827:2009.

Easy to service, cover and recover with cladding material.

Easy to operate.

Cost effective.

Site Selection and Layout

The following points were considered while selecting a site for protective structure.

It should be well connected to the market for supply of sales and produce.

It should have provision for future expansion.

The area required for protective structure should be selected on the basis of type of crop, land holding capacity of farmer etc.

The location should be away from large plants and multi-storeyed building to prevent their shadows on the protective structure.

The site should be well drained.

Orientation

The orientation of the protective structure is one of the most important factors. Following points were considered while selecting the orientation of protective structure.

The light level in the protective structure should be adequate and uniform for proper growth of the plants.

The magnitude of shadow depends on the season and angle of sun and it varies with season to season. Therefore, latitude and altitude of the area was considered while selecting the orientation of protective structure.

The longitudinal south side was used as sun.

Material used for construction of protective structure

The proposed naturally ventilated protective structure was constructed by using locally available materials such as GI square pipes, cement, sand, polythene sheet, shade net etc. The material was selected according to the design requirement of the structure.

GI Square shape pipes

GI square pipes are cheaper, light in weight and easy to handle. GI pipes have superior finish and anti-rust coating, so it provides greater resistance to corrosion. The 30 mm size square pipe was used for making frame of structure and 20 mm size square pipe was used for support.

Polythene sheet

The UV stabilized polythene film protects the crop from ultraviolet rays and creates a greenhouse effect. The UV stabilized polythene sheet of 200 microns was used as covering material for the protective structure.

Shade net

Shade net in protective structure was used for protecting various crops against excess of wind speed, damage from birds as well as rodents. It modifies the microclimate of crop by altering the percentage of shade which is the result of the reduction in intensity of light and heating parameters. It was made up of high-density polyethylene (HDPE) and available in various color and shading effects. A green-coloured shade net having a 50 per cent shading effect was used in research work.

Profile and spring

The profile and spring were used to fix the polythene sheet with the roof of the protective structure. The length of the profile was 2 m and self-driven screws were fitted in the profile at 1 m distance. The length of spring was 1 m and it was placed above the polythene sheet inside the profile.

Full Thread Nut Bolt

The 0.050 m (2") size full thread nut bolts were used for joining the frame of structure.

Cement

Cement is a binder used for construction that sets, hardens, and adheres to other material to bind them together. The foundation work of protection structure was done by using portland cement.

g. Sand

Sand is a granular material composed of finely divided rock and mineral particles. Sand has various compositions but is defined by its grain size. Crushed sand (grit) was used in concrete making for the foundation of a column.

Development of crop protective structure

The crop protective structure consists of following components.

Side and Opposite Wall

Front (Long) Wall

Frame

Rafter

Purlin

Door

Ventilation

Cladding Material

Gutter

A protected structure has two distinct segments i.e. frame and glazing material. Galvanized Iron steel pipe as a structural member along with wide width unstabilized polyethylene sheet was used.

Side and opposite wall

A Galvanized Iron square pipes having length of 2 m × 2.5 m with thickness of 40 mm was used for making Side and opposite wall.

Front (Long) wall

A GI square pipe having length of 5 m with 40 mm thickness square pipe was used for making Front (long) wall and opposite long wall.

Frame

A six GI square pipes having same height 2 m, each pipe is fixed at a distance of 1.25 m on front side, back side and four pipes having same

height 2 m at a distance of 0.86 m on east and west side of frame, in order to support the weight of structure properly.

Rafter

In structural component rafter is the primary supporter of protection structure. Rafter was generally place on 0.609, 0.914 or 1.219 m centers based on the energy requirements to hold the whole structure. A GI square pipe having length 2.9 m and thickness of 40 mm was used making of rafter.

Purlin

Purlin provide horizontal supports that run from rafter to rafter. All the structural components 1.219 to 2.438 m apart based on the magnitude of the protection structure. Purlin used in high wind area to provide additional support, connected by cross tie. fixed three GI square pipes having thickness 25 mm, every at a distance 0.966 m which is parallel to length fixed with nut bolt mechanism to increase and decrease the length of rafter.

Door

Build the frame of door 1 m × 0.5 m and lock them together with welding. Attached the door to the frame with several metal hinges, after making secure it is to structure.

Ventilation

The vent opener (1×0.833 m) was provided to open ventilation windows to the side wall from each side. The side vent allows to cool air to flow into the sides of structure. Some wind is necessary to move air through the structure. The area of the Ventilation was equal to 1/5th to 1/6th of the structure floor area. (Sevgican et al. 2000)

Cladding Material

UV stabilized 200-micron transparent plastic films conforming Indian Standard (IS 15827:2009) multilayered, anti-drip, anti-fog, diffused, clear and having minimum 85 % level of light transmittance was used as cladding material. All joints of plastic film fixed with two-way aluminum profile with suitable locking arrangement along with curtain top. Zigzag high carbon steel with spring action wire of 2- 3 mm diameter was inserted to fix shade net into aluminum profile. UV stabilized 50 % shading net with manually operated mechanism for expanding and retracting was used. (Greenhouse reference manual,2011)

Gutter

Gutter was fixed at the bottom of east west side of structure for collecting the roof rainwater which is used for irrigation purpose.

Table 1: Technical Specification of crop protective structure

Sr. No.	Parameters	Dimensions
1.	Length of protective structure	5 m
2.	Width of protective structure	2.5 m
3.	Distance between Side poles (side wall)	0.833 m
4.	Distance between Centre poles (Front wall)	1.25 m
5.	Height up to gutter (Front wall)	2.0 m
6.	Height up to top (back wall)	3.5 m
7.	Side ventilation	0.833 m ²
8.	Length of Rafter	2.9 m
9.	Distance between purlin to rafter	0.966 m
10.	Angle of Inclination	32.26°
11.	Orientation	South Facing (East-West)
12.	Covering	200 μ LDPE sheet
13.	Door	0.5 m ²

Fig. Front View

Fig. Side View

Fig. Back View

Fig. Isometric View

Schematic View of Protective Structure

Results and Discussions

Weekly variation of climatological parameters

The measurement of the different environmental parameters (Temperature, relative humidity, solar radiation and wind velocity) were recorded and weekly variation in climatological parameters is shown in fig. 1.

Fig.1: Weekly variation in climatological data

It was revealed that maximum inside and outside temperature of crop protective structure was found to be 35.98 °C and 33.34°C, respectively during 20th MW followed by 35.82 °C and 33.18 °C, respectively in 21st MW and 35.67 °C and 33.03 °C, respectively in 19th MW was observed. It was observed that the minimum inside and outside temperature of crop protective structure was found to be 24.84°C and 23.64 °C, respectively during 28th MW followed by 25.05 °C and 23.74 °C, respectively during 27th MW and 25.09 °C and 23.89 °C, respectively during 26th MW was observed.

It was revealed that maximum inside and outside solar intensity of crop protective structure was found to be 196.66 W/m² and 518.2 W/m², respectively during 20th MW followed by 194.63 W/m² and 517.80 W/m², respectively in 21st MW and 164.57 W/m² and 515.86 W/m², respectively in 19th MW.

It was observed that the minimum inside and outside solar intensity of crop protective structure was found to be 61.90 W/m² and 122.36 W/m², respectively during 28th MW followed by 61.90 W/m² and 122.36

W/m², respectively during 27th MW and 62.21 W/m² and 122 W/m², respectively during 26th MW.

It was revealed that maximum inside and outside relative humidity of crop protective structure was found to be 28.74% and 32.78 %, respectively during 14th MW followed by 27.41 % and 31.45 %, respectively in 15th MW and 27.09 % and 30.46 %, respectively in 16th MW was observed.

It was revealed that minimum inside and outside relative humidity of crop protective structure was found to be 25.71 % and 29.75 %, respectively during 20th MW followed by 25.87 % and 29.91 %, respectively in 21st MW and 26.42 % and 30.21 %, respectively in 19th MW was observed.

It was revealed that maximum inside and outside solar intensity of crop protective structure was found to be 196.66 W/m² and 518.2 W/m², respectively during 20th MW followed by 194.63 W/m² and 517.80 W/m², respectively in 21st MW and 164.57 W/m² and 515.86 W/m², in 19th MW.

It was revealed that minimum inside and outside solar intensity of crop protective structure was found to be 183.63 W/m² and 498.77 W/m², respectively during 14th MW followed by 187.09 W/m² and 511.31 W/m², respectively in 15th MW and 188.89 W/m² and 506.83 W/m², respectively in 16th MW was observed.

Conclusions:

It was observed that the temperature inside the crop protective structure is higher as compared to open field whereas the solar intensity is less as compared to open field during no load evaluation period of protective structure.

References

1. **Arora S.K., Singh Vijay Pal Godaram A.K., Bhatia A.K. and Raj Pal Singh. 2005.** Screening vegetable hybrids for greenhouse production. International Conference on plastic culture and Precision Farming” held at The Ashok, Chanakyapuri, New Delhi (17th Nov. to 21st Nov., 2005). Book of Abstract, Abstract No. ICPPF/036/GH/07 : 25.
2. **Bersani C., Ouammni, A., Sacile R., Zero E. 2020.** Model Predictive Control of Smart Greenhouses as the Path towards Near Zero Energy Consumption. *Energies*,13: 3647.
3. **Bhatnagar P. K., Vedprakash K. C., Srivastava V. K. and Sharma A. K. 1990.** Production of vegetables in polythene green house during winter in mid hills of Uttar Pradesh. *Progressive Horticulture*, 22 (1-4): 97-100.

4. **Chandra Pritam, Sirohi, N.P., Behera T.K. and Singh A.K. 2000.** Cultivating vegetables in polyhouse. *Indian Horticulture*, 45 (4): 17 and 32.
5. **Cheema D.S., Kaur P., Onkar Singh Dhunna, Singh P., Kaur S., Kaur Sundeep and Haliwal M.S. 2003.** studied the comparison between the tomatoes crop raised under the open field condition and under the net house conditions Haryana J. Hort. Sci. 32 (3 and 4): 288-289.
6. **Devic M., Dimitrijevic A. 2004.** Greenhouse energy consumption and energy efficiency, International conference, Russe, Bulgaria (<http://www.ru.acad.bg/baer/BugGHRad.pdf>)
7. **Ilic Z., Milenkovic L., Durovka M. and Kapoulas N. 2011.** The effect of color shade nets on the greenhouse climate and pepper yield. *Proceeding: 46th Croatian and 6th International Symposium on Agriculture, Opatija, Croatia*, pp. 529-32.
8. **Lal S. and Kanaujia S. P. 2013.** Integrated nutrient management in capsicum under low cost polyhouse condition. *Annals Hort.*, 6(2): 170-177.
9. **Mishra G.P., Singh N., Kumar H., Singh S.B. 2010.** Protected Cultivation for Food and Nutritional Security at Ladakh. *Defence Science Journal.*;61:219-230.
10. **Praveen Kote1, D.M Chandargi2 and Vijaylaxmi B. Somanatti 2020,** Doubling Farmers Income: An Insight Into Concepts, Views And Strategies In India ,Vol. X, Issue Xxxiii, April 2020 *Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601* , 750-754.
11. **Rai D. S., Yadav K. K. and Patel R. K. 1992.** Studies on shelf life of capsicum grown under protected and open conditions. *J. Agric. Sci.* 34: 3-4.
12. **R. S. Patode1, M. B. Nagdeve2, Rane Wankhade3, C. B. Pande4, R. S. Mali5 and V. P. Pandagale6 2019,** Mpaact Assessment Of Soil And Water Conservation Structures For Yield Enhancement And Doubling Farmers Income At Kajaleshwar-Warkhed Watershed, Vol. Viii, Special Issue(B), Nahep Icar Sponsored, International Conference On Eares-2019, At Dr.Pdkv Akola, *Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601*, Pp 80-82.
13. **Seema M. Pande, Pradnya S. Kadam and Sonali D. Zamre, 2019,** Doubling The Farmers Income Option And Challenges Review Vol. Viii, Special Issue(B), Nahep Icar Sponsored, International Conference On Eares-2019, At Dr.Pdkv Akola *Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601*, Pp 65-67.